

THERMAL BEHAVIOR OF SUGARCANE BAGASSE/PP COMPOSITES USING LIGNIN AS COMPATIBILIZER AGENT

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1 General Introduction

In recent years, natural fibers have drawn considerable attention as substitutes to the synthetic fibers such as glass and carbon fibers, as a result in strong growth from ecological concern, environmental attentiveness and new rules regulations [1]. The use of vegetal fibers as reinforcement in polymers presents many advantages, such as the low cost of natural fibers, low cost, low abrasion in processing equipment, low density, they are obtained from renewable sources and additionally, the use of these fibers could minimize environmental pollution due to their biodegradability [1,2].

Among the existing natural fibers, sugarcane bagasse and straw have been used as fillers in composite materials [3,4]. Brazil is the greatest sugarcane producer in the world [5]. The sugarcane is cultivated in southeast and northeast portions of the country, and for 2012–2013, the production was over 595 million tons. The material removed before the cane is crushed, is called straw. One ton of sugarcane cultivated produces 140 kg of sugarcane straw. Sugarcane bagasse, as any other biomass, consist of three main macromolecules: cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, cellulose being the most abundant and best studied. Cellulose-based fibers are the most widely used, as biodegradable filler. Intrinsically, these fibers have a number of interesting mechanical and physical properties [6,7]. Their environmentally friendly character and technical and economic advantages make these fibers attractive for an increasing number of industrial sectors, including the automotive industry, as replacements for glass fibers [7].

Lignin is a cell wall component in all vascular plants and in the wood stems of arborescent angiosperms (hardwood) and gymnosperms (softwoods). Lignin

acts as a water sealant in the stems and plays an important role in controlling water transport through the cell wall, and as a stiffener to give the stem its resistance against wind and gravity forces [8]. Lignin is a high molecular weight thermoplastic copolymer with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of approximately 90°C. Lignin is not hydrolyzed by acids, but it is soluble in hot alkali.

Shortcomings associated with natural fibers have to be overcome before using them as reinforcements in polymer composites [9]. It is well know that compatibility between lignocellulosic material and the polymer matrix plays a crucial role in determining the properties of a composite [10]. The most serious concern is the hydrophilic character of natural fiber, which leads to low compatibility with hydrophobic polymer matrices and also to a poor dimensional stability [11]. There are a wide variety of treatments that can be used to improve fiber-matrix adhesion in composites, as literature suggests ways to modify the fiber surface increasing the fiber/matrix adhesion [9]. However, chemical modification adds another step in the composite's preparation, hence very likely increasing the production cost [12].

An alternative to chemical treatments are the use of natural materials as compatibilizers in composite structure. Natural wood and plant fibers are constituted of cellulose fibers consisting of helically wound cellulose microfibrils, bound together by an amorphous lignin matrix. This make-up of wood suggests the potential of lignin to act as a compatibilizer between the hydrophilic natural fiber reinforcement and a hydrophobic matrix polymer [8]. Additionally, lignin has a complex and non-uniform structure with aliphatic and aromatic constituents [2]. Due to this, lignin has been investigated as compatibilizer agent in polymer composites [10,13]. Its utilization is justified by the presence of aliphatic

and polar groups, that can improve the compatibility between hydrophobic polymers and natural fibers [2].

In this work, it was proposed that lignin would improve fiber-to-matrix adherence and as a result the composites obtained would have better thermal and mechanical properties. Sugarcane bagasse fibers were chosen for the reinforcement because of the availability and cost effectiveness of this material in Brazil. Polypropylene (PP) was selected as matrix, as this is used in a variety of applications, and has industrially relevant properties. Sugarcane bagasse was pretreated by diluted acid, delignified, treated with xylanase and bleached. Lignin was obtained by the acid precipitation of the black liquor from the delignification step. Polypropylene (PP) composites reinforced from 5 to 40 wt% of bleached cellulose fibers and from 5 to 20%wt/wt of lignin from sugarcane bagasse were prepared in a thermokinetic mixer. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry was performed in order to evaluate the thermal properties of the obtained materials.

2 Experimental

2.1 Obtainment of bleached cellulose

In natura sugarcane bagasse was pretreated with 1% (wt/v) sulfuric acid solution at 120°C for 10 min, followed by a delignification step with 1% (wt/v) sodium hydroxide solution at 100°C for 1 h. The solid:liquid ratio was 1:10 (wt/v) for both processes. After this, treatment with xylanase (Pulpzyme) was carried out in polypropylene bags at 50°C for 2 h. The consistency of medium was 10% (wt/wt), and it was used 36 IU of enzyme per gram of pulp. The obtained pulp was submitted to an alkaline extraction with 5% (wt/v) NaOH (solid:liquid ratio 1:10) for 1 h at 65°C. The resulting material was chelated with EDTA 0.5% (wt/wt) for 30 min at 70°C in polyethylene bags, on a consistency of 10% (wt/wt) and, bleached with hydrogen peroxide. The bleaching of pulp was carried out in polyethylene bags placed in thermostat bath at 70°C for 1h, pH 8.0 to 12.2, on a consistency of 3% (wt/wt) and hydrogen peroxide (5% v/v). To minimize the effect of cellulose depolymerization by peroxide, it was added 0.5% (wt/v) MgSO₄·7H₂O, previously dissolved in distilled water.

2.2 Obtainment of Lignin

Lignin was obtained by the acid precipitation (pH 2,0), using H₂SO₄, of the black liquor from the delignification step. The precipitated material was washed until neutral pH was achieved.

2.3 Preparation of composites

Polypropylene (PP) composites reinforced with 5 to 40 wt% of bleached cellulose fibers and using 5 to 20%wt/wt of lignin, as coupling agent, both obtained from sugarcane bagasse, were prepared in a thermokinetic mixer at 5250 rpm. After mixing, the composites were cooled with water and after that, ground to 13 mm. The composites were dried in an oven at 80°C for 3 h and they were evaluated by thermal analysis. PP used as matrix was kindly provided by Braskem (Brazil).

2.4 Processes yields

The processes yields were determined by the weight difference before the step concerned and the weight at the end of this same step. The yield can be given by:

$$Y = \left(\frac{w}{W} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

where: Y (%) = the reaction yield in percentage;
w = weight of the material in the reaction step (g);
W = weight in previous step (g);

2.5 Chemical composition of lignocellulosic materials

The modified Klason method was utilized [14,15]. Samples (2.0g) of *in natura*, pretreated and

delignified, treated with xylanase, extracted with alkali and bleached with hydrogen peroxide sugarcane bagasse were treated with 10.0 mL of 72% H₂SO₄. After 7 min stirring at 45°C, 25 mL of water was added to the mixture, which was post-hydrolyzed under 1.05 bar for 30 min. The product was filtered and the insoluble portion (Klason lignin) was quantified. The hydrolysate was filtered in a Sep-Pak C18 cartridge, and analysed by high-performance liquid chromatography in a Shimadzu LC10 chromatograph with Aminex HPX-87H column at 45°C. The mobile phase was 0.005 mol.L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ at 0.6 mL.min⁻¹. The hydrolysis products were determined by refraction index and quantified by using calibration curves. Soluble lignin was determined as described by Gouveia et al. [15] using absorption at 280 nm of alkaline solutions obtained from the hydrolysate. The concentration of cellulose was determine by the addition of anhydrous – glucose, cellobiose and HMF, besides the amount of polyoses was determined through the sum of the anhydrous – xylose, arabinose and furfural [14,15].

2.5 Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA)

TGA was carried out using a thermal analyser of TA Instruments (model SDT Q600), in N₂ atmosphere at 10°C min⁻¹ heating rate, from 30 to 650°C.

2.7 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC was carried out in a calorimeter from TA Instruments SDT Q600, in N₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°C min⁻¹, from 30 to 650 °C, in a sealed vessel.

3 Results

3.1 Chemical composition of lignocellulosic materials

The analysis of chemical composition of bagasse *in natura* and pre-treated, reported in Table 1, together with the process yield 65.9%, revealed that 77.4% of hemicellulose (Figure 1) present in

bagasse *in natura* was solubilized. This kind of pre-treatment causes the solubilization of hemicelluloses [17], reduces the crystallinity of cellulose and increases the porosity of the materials [18]. As hemicellulose has a more amorphous and morphological structure of greater access to chemicals than cellulose (FENGEL;WEGENER .1989), which has a structure with higher crystallinity, the acid present during pre-treatment causes hydrolysis of hemicelluloses, mainly by removing them from the pretreated material. In addition, there was also loss of cellulose during pre-treatment, which was 17.6% (Figure 1), and probably much of amorphous cellulose or of low crystallinity making cellulosic fraction more susceptible to the action of other reagents. There was also a slight loss of lignin, about 9%. Lignin is not greatly removed during pretreatment, due to condensation reactions suffered in acidic conditions. These reactions are undesirable because they avoid the solubilization of lignin.

Tab 1. Chemical composition of sugarcane bagasse, pretreated bagasse, delignified pulp, treated with xylanase pulp, extracted with NaOH pulp and bleached pulp

Components	In natura bagasse (%)	Pretreated Bagasse(%)	Delignified pulp (%)	Treated with xylanase pulp (%)	Extracted with NaOH pulp (%)	Bleached Pulp (%)
Cellulose	46.4 ± 0.3	58.1 ± 1.2	71.5 ± 1.2	72.2 ± 1.1	77.9 ± 0.5	82.8 ± 0.6
Hemicellulose	23.9 ± 0.3	6.2 ± 0.3	3.5 ± 0.4	4.0 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.1
Lignin	29.1 ± 0.7	33.7 ± 1.7	22.7 ± 0.1	22.7 ± 0.5	16.9 ± 0.1	11.1 ± 0.3
Asher	1.5 ± 0.6	2.0 ± 0.3	2.5 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.9	1.0 ± 0.1

The pulp obtained after the alkaline delignification presented about lignin 22.7% (Table 1), a lower value compared to amount of lignin in present in *in natura* bagasse. Approximately 50% (Figure 1) of the lignin present in the pretreated material was solubilized after the process. It was also observed a removal of 69% (Figure 1) of hemicellulose. Furthermore, about 9% of cellulose was dissolved. In alkaline medium, cellulose can suffer hydrolysis and peeling reactions occur. These reactions are undesirable because the average length of the chain decreases and also because of the loss of sugars, carbohydrates removed can be are converted into various organic acids, hydroxy, which reduce the effective alkali concentration in cooking liquor [20,21]. The process yield obtained for the delignification step was 73.9%.

Figure 1. Components loss during the obtention of bleached fibers (1-pretreatment; 2-delignification; 3-xylanase treatment; 4-NaOH extraction; 5-bleaching)

The treatment with xylanase was not successful in solubilizing the hemicellulosic fraction, still present in pulp after the delignification step. This probably occurred due to a low enzymatic activity of xylanase used in this work, on average 330.32 UI/mL, which prevented the expected removal. A small fraction of lignin was removed, about 7.2% (Figure 1). The solubilization of hemicellulose and lignin is due to the fact that the removal of the hemicellulosic structure by xylanase breaks the lignin-carbohydrate links and facilitates the removal of lignin fragments that were formed in previous treatments. Cellulose was not so dissolved, about 0.4% (Figure 1), thus leaving the pulp obtained after the treatment with xylanase a 72.2% content (Table 1). The process yield derived for this step was 98.7%.

Alkaline extraction had a process yield of 88.30% step caused a high loss of lignin, about 30%, as can be observed in Table 1. There was also removal of hemicellulose and cellulose. In alkaline medium, the carbohydrates suffer peeling reactions, which leads to its degradation. The enzymatic treatment carried out previously let the hemicelluloses more susceptible to this kind of reaction, as a result this component had a high degree of removal, about 46% (Figure 1). Although cellulose was more exposed due to the removal of part of hemicelluloses and lignin in previous treatment steps, it was not greatly solubilized, mainly due to its cristallinity, which prevents the breaking of cellulosic structure.

The removal of lignin, during bleaching with peroxide step, was accentuated approximately 40%

(Table 1). It was also noticed the solubilization of hemicellulose, around 46% and there was no solubilization of cellulose (Figure 1). The process yield of this last stage was 95.3%, demonstrating that there was no significant loss of mass after bleaching, despite the removal of much of the residual lignin still present in the extracted pulp.

In the route of cellulose extraction studied, it was obtained a material with a high content of cellulose, low hemicellulose content, but with still some lignin remaining, showing that the process used could have been more effective at removing hemicellulose and lignin. On the other hand, there were also significant losses of cellulose. At the end of the whole process of obtaining cellulose, the total loss of this component was 28.7% (Figure 1). This fact is undesirable, since the goal of the work is the use of cellulose, and this loss ends up affecting the final yield of the process, and can make it unfeasible. However, the loss of lignin was about 84%, a result quite satisfactory, but far from ideal. The loss of lignin was evidenced throughout the process. For the hemicelluloses, total loss along the way was nearly 100%, principally in the pre-treatment step.

3.2 Thermal analysis of composite materials

Thermal analyses are important tools for the characterization of polymeric materials, since the thermal stability consists of important property to assess possible applications. Lignocellulosic fibers were submitted to intense heat during composite fabrication. Therefore, a thermal analysis study was necessary to determine the influence of fibers addition into polymer on thermal stability of composites and to confirm any degradation process during composites production. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to verify the thermal stability and degradation of composites, of cellulose fibers, lignin and pure polypropylene (PP). This characterization allowed not only to evaluate the limit of temperature to which this material can be submitted, but also to study the influence of the fiber/lignin content in the polymeric matrix. The thermal degradation and stability were evaluated by TG (thermogravimetric) curves.

Figure 2. TG curves of PP, Cellulose, Lignin, PP + 30%cellulose + 0% lignin and PP + 30%cellulose + 20% lignin

Figure 2 shows the TG curve for cellulose fibers, lignin and pure PP and composite reinforced with 30% (wt/wt) of cellulose + 0% (wt/wt) of lignin and 30% (wt/wt) of cellulose + 20% (wt/wt) of lignin. The TGA curve obtained for cellulose fibers showed that below 100°C, the weight loss is associated with loss of water due to moisture content. Despite the fibers being dried before the analysis, the total elimination of water is not possible due to the hydrophilic character of the fibers [22]. Also it can be seen, that the fibers have thermal stability up to approximately 275°C, when the thermal decomposition starts, corresponding to the beginning of the decomposition of hemicelluloses, followed by cellulose. Around 350°C there is the beginning of another process of decomposition, probably involving lignin bonds, proceeding rapidly with the increasing of temperature.

The TGA curve for lignin is also shown in Figure 2. Great differences were found among the pyrolysis behaviors of these two materials. Cellulose pyrolysis was focused at a lower temperature range (315-400°C). When temperature was higher than 400°C, almost all cellulose was pyrolyzed with a very low solid residue left. Instead, lignin was more difficult to decompose. Its decomposition happened slowly under the whole temperature range from ambient to 650°C, but at a very low mass rate. The solid residue left from lignin pyrolysis was the highest. The differences in the inherent structures and chemical nature of the three components

possibly account for the different behaviors observed.

Tab 2. Weight loss at different temperatures and degradation temperature peak of polypropylene and cellulose/lignin/PP composites

Samples	Weight loss (%)						Degradation temperature peak (°C)
	100°C	200°C	300°C	400°C	500°C	600°C	
Cellulose	5.2	5.57	16.05	81.48	85.1	86.48	352
Lignin	4.53	6.24	19.94	47.25	57.27	61.61	350.1
PP pure	0.12	0.64	0.74	2.16	97.97	97.99	454.1
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	0.13	0.89	1.77	5.87	98.15	98.22	347.2-457.3
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	0.22	1.13	2.83	9.49	98.33	98.39	165.6-351.0-459.4
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	0.23	0.81	2.89	11.24	96.5	96.88	318.1-460.7
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	0.33	0.65	3.79	14.49	91.88	92.69	354.8-461.4
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	0.23	0.67	2.35	9.28	96.6	96.71	345.1-457.8
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	0.28	0.78	2.73	12.66	98.17	98.44	357.8-468.6
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	0.89	1.24	4.98	18.89	89.87	90.78	354.7-461.3
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	0.33	1.04	3.95	15.88	94.38	94.92	380.8-461.8
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	0.46	1.78	4.94	18.27	98.31	98.63	344.6-461.4
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	0.5	1.45	4.17	19.78	92.19	92.8	351.3-463.8
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	0.41	1.29	4.88	22.58	92.51	93.19	352.0-463.8
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	0.31	1.76	6.66	26.68	88.16	89.36	162.3-352.8-464.7
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	0.53	2.23	6.68	25.57	93.83	94.24	162.2-342.5-465.9
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	0.57	1.63	5.99	28.05	91.99	92.67	348.8-466.3
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	1.44	2.06	6.72	30.22	92.63	93.43	352.2-464.9
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	1.55	2.47	8.17	33.55	85.5	86.75	352.2-468.7
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	0.82	2.47	7.35	30.34	92.93	93.67	162.9-342.9-466.9
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	1.45	2.02	7.88	33.71	91.49	92.28	347.6-467.9
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	1.3	2.69	8.46	35.29	91.2	91.99	347.2-469.3
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	1.93	2.88	9.07	34.55	90.28	91.39	348.8-465.8

TGA curves obtained for the pure PP and the composites obtained in this work are shown in Figure 2 and the weight loss at different temperatures and degradation temperature peak os polypropylene, cellulose, lignin and composites are shown in Table 3. The small weight loss up to 100°C is related to the moisture content of the material. Above this temperature, it can also occur, the volatilization of some water molecules tightly bound to the fibers. Comparing the TGA curves of pure PP and the composites reinforced with cellulose fibers it can be observed a similar behaviour. The TGA curves indicate that the decomposition process of the PP matrix occurs in only one step, while for the composites this process occurs in two steps. The first step is the decomposition of the fibers and the second of the matrix. It may be noticed that when a greater amount of reinforcement was added to the matrix, there was a reduction in thermal stability of the composite.

Table 2 shows the weight loss of the materials for each temperature range. Analyzing the table results, it was noticed that up to 400° C, the PP do not lose much weight, but above this temperature the weight loss is fast. The PP/celulose composite, without the addition of lignin, have a initial decomposition temperature smaller than the composites in which lignin was used as an additive. The greater thermal stability of these materials is due to the fact that lignin acts as a protective barrier

against the thermal degradation [23]. The high thermal stability of lignin is due to the presence of complex phenylpropanoid units, which consist of aromatic phenyl groups. These aromatic structures are very stable. Moreover, the presence of hydroxyl groups also contributes to stability, since the electrons paired not also come into resonance, increasing the stability of aromatic structures and preventing breakage that occurs only at high temperatures [2, 24,25].

Figure 3. DSC curves of PP, Cellulose, Lignin, PP + 30% cellulose + 0% lignin and PP + 30% cellulose + 20% lignin

Figure 3 shows DSC curves for cellulose fiber, lignin and pure PP and composite reinforced with 30% (wt/wt) of cellulose + 0% (wt/wt) of lignin and 30% (wt/wt) of cellulose + 20% (wt/wt) of lignin. The DSC curve of the cellulosic fibers presents an endothermic peak at 350°C. This peak demonstrates is related to thermal degradation of cellulose and hemicellulose portion still present in the bleached pulp. Comparing the DSC curves between the PP and the composite, it can be noticed that both have three endothermic peaks. The first endothermic peak (below 100° C), moisture loss, was observed in all samples. The behavior of the curves of composites presents profile and temperature peaks similar to PP. There are no significant changes in the melting temperature of the PP after the addition of fibers, as can be seen in Table 3. However, the melting enthalpy has decreased considerably with the addition of reinforcement, indicating a decrease of crystallinity of the matrix. According to the literature, higher load levels would imply on the formation of smaller and less perfect crystals, since a smaller number of sites of polymeric molecules

would be gathered and there will be a greater number of impediments to their growth, resulting in a possible decrease in the degree of crystallinity [26]. The observed peaks close to 350°C are related to thermal decomposition of cellulose and hemicellulose portion, as it could be observed in the DSC curve of the fibers. The peak was also observed on the decomposition of the matrix (PP), near 450°C.

Tab 3. DSC results of PP and composites reinforced with cellulose and lignin from sugarcane bagasse

Sample	Melting			Degradation		
	T _{on} (°C)	T _{off} (°C)	ΔH _{melting} (J.g ⁻¹)	T _{on} (°C)	T _{off} (°C)	ΔH _{degradation} (J.g ⁻¹)
PP	164.3	149.0	17.8	438.3	430.5	333.0
PP + 5% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	165.9	152.1	15.9	439.1	430.1	410.5
PP + 5% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	166.6	152.5	14.8	460.5	429.2	391.3
PP + 5% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	165.7	151.3	14.4	461.6	427.6	361.3
PP + 5% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	164.9	152.4	14.5	461.4	426.7	288.1
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	165.2	152.2	14.5	461.3	433.0	373.0
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	166.1	151.6	14.5	461.7	429.5	361.1
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	164.7	151.4	14.1	461.4	428.2	247.8
PP + 10% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	165.0	151.8	13.5	462.0	428.8	300.0
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	166.0	154.8	11.5	464.4	437.2	282.8
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	164.3	151.4	14.9	464.4	434.2	268.4
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	164.8	151.9	13.3	463.7	432.9	232.8
PP + 20% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	164.3	156.9	16.2	464.2	430.2	188.9
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	165.0	150.2	14.1	466.1	437.0	256.7
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	163.8	151.9	15.1	466.7	432.8	217.8
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	164.1	152.0	13.1	464.6	425.5	209.2
PP + 30% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	163.8	152.2	13.3	468.6	431.3	331.0
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 0% Lignin	165.3	152.4	14.4	467.1	437.7	214.1
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 5% Lignin	164.4	151.7	13.0	467.7	434.5	137.4
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 10% Lignin	164.7	151.3	13.8	469.0	432.6	137.7
PP + 40% de Cellulose + 20% Lignin	163.8	152.2	14.7	464.9	425.4	173.8

4 Conclusions

Results revealed that the route chosen for obtaining cellulose was promising, but changes in the process must be carried in order to avoid losing large amounts of cellulose. At the final of the process of obtainment of bleached cellulose, the material had a great portion of cellulose and small portions of hemicelluloses and lignin. The TG curves indicate that the process of decomposition of the matrix (PP) occurs in only one stage, while for the composites this process occurs in two stages. The PP/celulose composite without the addition of lignin presented initial decomposition temperature smaller than the composites in which lignin was used as an additive. The behavior of DSC curves of composites presents profile and temperature peaks similar to PP. The addition of reinforcement in most studied ratios decreased the ΔH_{melting} of materials, indicating a decrease in the matrix cristalinity.

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